

PERFORMANCE OF THE RESTRICTED MEAN SURVIVAL TIME IN ANALYZING OVERALL SURVIVAL IN TRIALS STUDYING PERI-OPERATIVE OR NEOADJUVANT CHEMOTHERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH ESOPHAGEAL OR JUNCTIONAL CANCER

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We tested the performance of the restricted mean survival time (RMST)^{1,2} in analyzing overall survival (OS) in three randomized trials conducted in patients with esophageal or junctional cancer.³⁻⁵ These three trials were aimed at evaluating the impact on OS of different regimens of perioperative or neoadjuvant chemotherapy. Our methods for estimating RMST have previously been described elsewhere.⁶

Table 1 illustrates the results of our analysis. Two trials found a significant improvement in OS for the treatment group compared with the controls (Cross³ and FLOT⁴). The third found no significant difference (UKRMC⁵).

The comparison between the outcome measures based on RMST with the outcome measures based on traditional survival analysis (medians and hazard ratio [HR]) underscores two main findings:

1. when the trial does not find any significant difference between treated patients and controls, the values of traditional survival parameters are quite similar to those based on the RMST.
2. In contrast, when the trial finds a significant difference between treated patients and controls, the values of traditional survival parameters show a greater magnitude of incremental benefit compared with the magnitude estimated based on the RMST.

This finding, observed for peri-operative or neoadjuvant chemotherapy in patients with esophageal or junctional cancer, is in line with the information reported in numerous studies that have evaluated RMST in other disease conditions.¹

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Table 1. Characteristics of the 2 arms and values of RMST estimated from the time-to-event curves in the 3 randomised trials evaluated in the present analysis. Overall survival was the endpoint for these 6 curves.

Data-set	Cohort	t* (mos)	No. of patients/ events	HR (95%CI)	Median (mos)	RMST (mos) with 95%CI	Ratio RMST _c / RMST _t	Trial-specific gain (mos)**	
								According to medians	According to RMST
CROSS ³	CRT (neoadjuvant)	58	171/61	0.657 (0.495-0.871)	49.4	38.23 (34.42-42.05)	0.841	25.4	6.06
	surgery alone		188/83		24.0	32.17 (28.46-35.89)			
FLOT ⁴	FLOT (perioperative)	58	356/166	0.77 (0.63 -0.94)	50	39.40 (37.09-41.71)	0.91	15	3.56
	ECF/ECX (perioperative)		360/203		35	35.84 (33.55-38.14)			
UKRMC ⁵	ECX (neoadjuvant)	58	446/302	0.90 (0.77-1.05)	26.1	33.66 (31.80-35.52)	0.94	2.7	2.02
	CF (neoadjuvant)		451/327		23.4	31.64 (29.75-33.53)			

Abbreviations: HR, hazard ratio for the comparison of treatment arm vs controls; RMST: restricted mean survival time; mos, months; t*, milestone; CRT: neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy, FLOT: fluorouracil plus leucovorin, oxaliplatin and docetaxel; ECF/ECX: perioperative epirubicin and cisplatin plus either fluorouracil or capecitabine. ECX: epirubicin, cisplatin, and capecitabine; CF: cisplatin and fluorouracil.